

THE LIGHT FROM THE SHOVT

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Or about the shrine of His Holiness "Yusuf Khamadoni".

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"If if the economy is the body of society's life, its soul and spirit is spirituality. We new Uzbekistan set up as we decided to do, on two strong pillars we rely The first is the market principles based on strong economy. The second is the rich heritage of our ancestors and based on national values strong spirituality," he says

Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev.

When a person is in the dark, he naturally seeks the light and strives towards it. If he wants to get information about something, he will definitely turn to a book. There is a place in our country, located in the village of "*Beshmergan*", Shavat district, Khorezm region, where the great mystic Khoja Yusuf Hamadoni (Ulli pir), who spread the teachings of Sufism in Central Asia and founded the Khojagan order, spread knowledge, wisdom, jurisprudence, philosophy and logic from the order. is a shrine of His Holiness. Nowadays, for pilgrimage to the whole world, it is as if the sun is spreading light, opening its bosom and saying, come and feel my touch.

Of course, such opportunities have been created by our President as a result of the last five years of reforms, the necessary political-legal, social-economic and scientific-educational foundations for the establishment of New Uzbekistan in our country. Based on this, favorable conditions were created for foreign investors, businessmen and other industry workers, including tourists, and foreign tourism was launched.

Of course, scholars know which place is comfortable to live and create. In the same way, the pilgrimage site of His Holiness Khoja Yusuf Hamadoni is a place with fresh air, yellow fruits, four seasons, peaceful and calm, and the presence of mulberry trees over 100 years old is a clear proof of this. That is why the number of local and foreign tourists is increasing day by day.

Photo 1.

According to the representatives of the local people who went on Hajj trip to Ka'batullah, if the people of Arabia want to come here for a pilgrimage, they say that we want to go to the old Khorezm, the 360 saints there, as well as the shrine of His Holiness Khoja Yusuf Hamadani.

For example, when Yusuf Hamadani came to Khorezm with Khoja Abdulkadir Gilani (Ghavsul A'zam), the founder of the "Qadiriya" leech, which is considered the first order of Sufism, Ghavsul A'zam prayed while standing on one leg. Then if they ask him why you prayed on one leg while your legs were idols, every inch of Khorezm is a shrine, the graves of most of the 360 saints who passed here are unknown, so I prayed on one leg for fear of accidentally stepping on their resting place with my foot. they answered.

According to the testimony of reliable sources, the lineage of Imam Yusuf Hamadani, the first caliph after the Prophet Muhammad, goes back to Abu Bakr Siddique.

His Holiness Yusuf Hamadani was born in 1048 AD (440 Hijri) in the village of Buzarjird, not far from the city of Hamadan, Iran. His full name is Sharif Abu Yaqub Yusuf ibn Ayyub Hamadani. His parents were pious people. His Holiness Yusuf Hamadani received his initial education in his village and learned to write letters. Later, he studied at a madrasa in the city of Isfahan.

His Holiness Yusuf Hamadani came to Baghdad in 1068 and started studying at the "Nizomiya" madrasa. At that time, Sheikh Abul Ishaq Shirazi, a mature scholar of his time, was the headmaster of the prestigious "Nizomiya" madrasa.

He paid special attention to his talented student Yusuf Hamadoni and taught fiqh, philosophy and logic. Shaykh Abul Ishaq Sherazi had a great role in Yusuf Hamadani's achievement of the highest status in the Sufi order. Yusuf Hamadoni lived in Baghdad for about 15 years and reached the level of a mature Sufism scholar. That person hangs a house and starts walking his leech. Soon his fame spread widely in the Eastern countries, and devoted murids from Arabia, India, Iran, Khurasan and Khorezm began to come to him and taught them the science of fiqh and hadith.

Photo 2.

In 1112, Melodiy Yusuf Hamadoni met Khoja Abdulqadir Gilani (Ghavsul Azam), the founder of the "Qadiriya" leech, which is considered the first order of Sufism in the city of Baghdad.

Even though His Holiness Yusuf Hamadoni formed his sect in the city of Baghdad, later in order to expand the scope of his teaching, he traveled to the countries of the Turanian land and made many disciples in the cities of Khorezm, Bukhara, Samarkand and Marv.

His Holiness Yusuf Hamadoni looks with great love and devotion to the land of Khorezm, which was the center of ancient culture and science in his youth. Yusuf Hamadani's heart is filled with enthusiasm for the contributions and discoveries of the world-renowned scholars Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorazmi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Abdullah Yusuf al-Khorazmi and Katib al-Khorazmi. Therefore, the great scholar aims to spread his sect in Khorezm and Mavarounnahr and travels to Khorezm with Khoja Hassan Andoki. Khoja Hassan Andokiy and they arrive in the city of Gurganch, the capital of Khorezmshahs. Khorezmshah welcomes dear guests with great hospitality and builds a luxurious house for the sheikh to conduct his sect. His Highness Hamadani conducted his leeches here and taught students of hadith and fiqh in prestigious madrasas. Hamadoni's stay in Khorezm dates back to 1105-1115. In 1116, he came to Bukhara and after staying there for a long time went to Samarkand. According to Gijduvani of Abdukholi, Hamadoni lived in "Khushrud" neighborhood of Samarkand. In the cities of Bukhara and Samarkand, he works together with his students Khoja Abdullah Barraki, Khoja Hasan Andoki, Khoja Ahmad Yassavi, Khoja Abdulkhalik Gijduvani.

Yusuf Hamadani had a conversation with Abdul Qasim Az-Zamakshari in Bukhara.

His Holiness Yusuf Hamadani made Hajj to March 37 Kabatullah throughout his life.

His Holiness Yusuf Hamadani died in Khirat and Marv in 1141 (535 Hijri).

Traditions say that if Yusuf Hamadani looked at sick and disabled people, especially those who were insane, or patted them on the back, they would recover from severe pain.

Yusuf Hamadani's works - the great scholar wrote down valuable works on Sufism, hadith and tawsir sciences. Among them are "*Rutbal ul-khayat*" (Criterium of Life), "*Risolai kashf*" (Discovery treatise), "*Risola dar adobi tariqat*" (Treatise on Tariqat etiquette), "*Risala fi annal kavna musakharrun lil-insan*" (*On the study of the human heart there are valuable works such as pamphlets*).

If you want to have more information about His Holiness Yusuf Hamadoni, as the saying goes, "*It is better to see once than to hear a thousand times*" if you visit the shrine.

References:

1. Ismailov, T. (2022). The light from the shovot or about the shrine of his holiness "yusuf khamadoni". Models and methods in modern science, 1(17), 12-15.

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CONFERENCES

